

ARTICLE

The Influence of Product Completeness, Price, Store Location and Promotion on the Purchase Intention of Sari Roti Products (Case Study of Alfamidi in Manado City, North Sulawesi Province)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of product completeness, price, store location, and promotion on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products at Alfamidi in Manado City, both simultaneously and partially. Alfamidi was chosen because it is one of the main retail chains that sells Sari Roti in Manado. A decrease in purchasing interest can have a negative impact on sales, so it is important to understand the factors that influence it. This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach. Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to 236 consumers who purchased Sari Roti products at 10 Alfamidi outlets with the highest sales in Manado City, from a population of 377 people. Sampling was carried out with inclusion criteria, with a sample range of 50 to 500 people in the period from September to October 2024. The analysis methods used include validity tests, reliability tests, classical assumption tests, hypothesis tests, and multiple linear regression using SPSS version 27. The results showed that product completeness, price, store location, and promotion had a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest simultaneously and partially. Therefore, Alfamidi and Sari Roti management need to consider these factors to increase consumer purchasing interest.

Keywords: Product Completeness, Price, Store Location, Promotion, Purchase Interest, Sari Roti, Alfamidi

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Introduction

Indonesia, with its rich diversity of food resources, has great potential to support food security through food diversification, including bakery products such as bread, cakes, and biscuits. In 2022, white bread consumption in Indonesia reached 18.4 kg/capita/year, although most of it uses imported wheat flour. There is an opportunity to replace it with local ingredients such as cassava mocaflour, which not only supports food independence but also adds nutritional value and sensory characteristics to the product, making bread play an important role in global food security and community welfare.

Globally, the bakery industry is experiencing significant product diversification due to changing consumer behaviors and increasingly busy lifestyles, driving demand for ready-to-eat, organic and nutritious breads. In Indonesia, the growth of the industry is driven by urbanization and rising living standards, which have contributed to increased purchasing power and demand for healthy and delicious bakery products. Innovations in bakery products, such as the use of local raw materials and efficient baking technologies, are key to meeting the needs of the growing market, with the global bakery industry market projected to reach \$9.3 billion by 2030. Amidst this, achieving the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to end hunger and malnutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture, relies heavily on increasing agricultural productivity and implementing sustainable agricultural practices that support ecosystems and climate change adaptation.

In Indonesia, various companies are competing to market innovative and quality bread products, one of which is PT Nippon Indosari Corpindo Tbk, the largest mass bread producer with the brands "Sari Roti," "Sari Kue," and "Sari Choco" which are known to be halal, quality, safe, and affordable. Since its establishment in 1995, the company has operated 14 factories and more than 88,000 points of sale throughout Indonesia, with Sari Roti widely known after listing its shares on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2010 (Sari Roti, 2024).

Despite having product advantages and a wide distribution network, Sari Roti sales in Manado City, North Sulawesi, have experienced a significant decline in the last two years. This decline was recorded at all mini market outlets such as Indomaret, Alfamart, and Alfamidi, with a sales decline of 10.3% in 2023 compared to the previous year. From the available data, Alfamidi outlets experienced the largest decline in sales, with a minus growth figure of -10.29%. This decline was caused by product stock problems, such as running out of stock or expired products, which caused even though promotions were carried out intensively, supply was insufficient to meet the spike in demand after the promotion, so that consumers felt disappointed and purchasing interest decreased (Sari Roti Management, 2024).

Internal issues such as product completeness and promotion, as well as pressure from competitors, are also significant reasons for the decline in Sari Roti sales in Manado. Competitors offer products with lower prices, attractive packaging, longer expiration dates, and aggressive promotions, which make consumers more sensitive to price and promotion. Monroe et al. (2019) emphasized that although price is the main factor in purchasing decisions, consumer perceptions of product value also greatly influence these

decisions. Prices that match consumer value and purchasing power significantly influence purchasing interest and decisions (Mauludi and Meditarisa, 2023). Ali and Malinda (2022); Saria and Nurmaning (2024) location variables affect consumer purchasing interest, with stores in strategic locations tending to attract more attention and increase sales.

Promotion is also an important element in marketing strategies to increase consumer interest in Sari Roti products. The right promotions, such as price discounts and special offers, can increase brand awareness and attract new consumers. However, Abbas et al. (2022) found that promotions do not always have a positive effect on sales if they are not accompanied by good management. Alfamidi carries out promotions through online and offline media, and has regular promotional programs such as Friday, Saturday, Sunday (JSM) promos, where Sari Roti products are usually bundled with other products.

Based on this description and the fact that there has been no similar research related to Sari Roti products at Alfamidi in Manado City, the author is interested in conducting research with the theme: "The Influence of Product Completeness, Price, Store Location, and Promotion on Purchase Interest of Sari Roti Products (Case Study of Alfamidi in Manado City, North Sulawesi)".

Research purposes

1. Analyzing the influence of Product Completeness, Price, Store Location and Promotion simultaneously on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products.
2. Knowing the partial influence of Product Completeness on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products
3. To find out the partial influence of price on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products
4. To find out the partial influence of store location on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products
5. To determine the partial influence of promotion on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products

Literature Review

Marketing Management

Marketing is an activity that acts as a bridge between two sectors, namely the production sector and the consumption sector. Every production sector wants its products to be delivered and owned by consumers. The company will do its best so that consumers are satisfied with the goods it produces (Taufik, 2023). According to the American Marketing Association (Yulianto et al., 2024), marketing management includes activities, a set of institutions, and processes that aim to create, communicate, deliver, and exchange valuable offerings for customers, clients, partners, and the general public. Marketing management can be said to be a science and art, where it is not only knowledge, but also a skill that can be different and unique depending on who applies it (Taufik, 2023).

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention describes a person's tendency or interest in a particular product or service, which is shown through the intention or desire to buy (Prasetya et al., 2020). According to Amri (2019), Purchase intention is a type of consumer behavior that appears as a response to an object, indicating the consumer's desire to buy. Linda and Hendro (2024) state that Purchase intention is a representation of a person's attitude

towards a particular object, which is very suitable for measuring behavior towards a particular product, service, or brand. According to Septyadi et al. (2022), Purchase intention is identified through the following indicators: Transactional interest, Referential interest, Preferential interest, and Exploratory interest.

Product Completeness

Firmansyah (2019) added that not only goods, but also services that can be bought and sold are also considered products. Products, thus, include all things that can be traded between sellers and buyers, either in the form of physical goods or services. Product completeness refers to the condition or quality of a product that is fully equipped with all components, features, information, or elements needed to meet customer expectations and achieve the intended purpose. A complete product list is one that provides all the important attributes, functionality, and specifications that customers generally look for when they consider making a purchase (Bluestone PIM, 2024). Product completeness indicators according to Ramazan (2024), product completeness indicators include: Diversity of goods sold in supermarkets, Variation of products sold and Availability of products sold.

Price

According to Sadiyah (2021), price is an amount of money or value exchanged by consumers to obtain benefits, ownership, or use of a product or service. Hurriyati (2019) explains that price is an effort to determine the income of a business by determining critical point decisions in the marketing mix. According to Nastiti and Rahayu (2019), price perception is related to how consumers fully understand price information and give it deep meaning to them. Tonce and Joseph (2022) describe price indicators, namely; Price affordability, Price suitability with product quality, Price competitiveness and Price suitability with benefits.

Store Location

Kotler and Keller (2021), location in the marketing mix is defined as an area or channel where products or services are distributed by a company so that they can be reached by target customers efficiently and effectively. Jamlean et al. (2022), store location includes various marketing activities aimed at facilitating and facilitating the storage and distribution of goods and services from producers to consumers in a particular area. Barung et al., (2023) argue that location is a place where a business is established which greatly influences consumer interest in making purchases. Location indicators according to Imanulah et al. (2022), namely: Access, Visibility, Traffic, Parking, Expansion, Competitive environment, and Government Regulations.

Promotion

According to Syahputra (2019), promotion is "a communication activity carried out by a person or a company with the wider community, where the aim is to introduce something (goods/services/brands/companies) to the public and at the same time influence the wider community to buy and use the product". Ningrum et al. (2023), stated that promotion is "Part of Marketing Communication, meaning the activity of marketers who try to disseminate information, influence/persuade, and/or remind the target market of the company and its products so that they are willing to accept, buy and be loyal to the products offered by the company concerned so that in the end it is expected to increase sales in the company". According to Wangsa et al. (2022), there are five promotion indicators, namely: Advertising, Sales Promotion, Personal Selling, Public Relations, and Direct Marketing.

Previous Research

Widia Priatna, et al (2023) in his research analyzed the influence of product completeness, service, and store location on consumer purchasing interest at Toko Bukupena Kartasura. The results showed that the product completeness variable had a simultaneous effect on consumer purchasing interest, while the service and store location variables had a positive effect on consumer purchasing interest at Toko Bukupena Kartasura.

Utari, et al (2021) analyzed the influence of product completeness, promotion, and location on purchasing interest in the city of Surabaya (East Java, Indonesia) in 2020. The results obtained showed that product completeness had the greatest influence on purchasing interest, while product promotion had a moderate influence, and product location had the smallest influence on purchasing interest.

Diansyah, and Utami (2022), analyzed the effect of price and promotion on purchase interest, with consumer behavior as a moderating variable. The results of the study showed that price and promotion have a significant effect on purchase interest, while consumer behavior also plays an important role. In addition, consumer behavior strengthens the effect of price and promotion on purchase interest.

Usman and Diyanti (2020), tested the influence of price, promotion, and word of mouth on consumer purchasing interest. The results of the study showed that the three variables, namely price, promotion, and word of mouth, have the same influence on purchasing interest.

Research Model

Description: Partial ; Simultaneous

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Literature Reviews, 2024

Hypothesis

H1: It is suspected that there is a simultaneous influence of product completeness, price, store location and promotion on the interest in purchasing Sari Roti products.

H2: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of product completeness on the Interest in Purchasing Sari Roti Products.

H3: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of price on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products.

H4: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of the store location on the interest in purchasing Sari Roti products.

H5: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of promotion on the interest in purchasing Sari Roti products

Methodology

This study uses a descriptive research type with a quantitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2019), descriptive research is a study that describes a condition or phenomenon according to the actual conditions found when the research is conducted, while quantitative research is a research method that uses data in the form of numbers and is analyzed statistically.

Research Object and Time

This research was conducted in 10 Alfamidi outlets according to clusters located in Manado City, North Sulawesi Province. The research activities took place from September to October 2024.

Method of collecting data

Data collection methods are procedures or techniques used by researchers to collect the information needed to achieve research objectives. This method is essential in the research process because the data obtained will be used to answer research questions and test the proposed hypotheses. Some data collection methods in this study include observation, interviews, questionnaires/surveys, and secondary data collection.

Population and Research Sample

Population is the entire group or set of individuals or objects that are the target of research (Sugiyono, 2019). The population in the study was all customers who had shopped at 10 Alfamidi Outlets in Manado City.

A sample is a part of a population that reflects the number and characteristics of the entire population. In order for the conclusions of the study to be generalized to the entire population, the sample taken must be truly representative (Sugiyono, 2021). The sample in this study was all data that met the inclusion criteria obtained from the distribution of questionnaires to customers at Alfamidi in Manado City from September 21 to October 05, 2024, with the provision that the number of samples was between 50 and 500 (Sugiyono, 2019), during the period of time the study was conducted. The samples obtained in the research period were 236 samples.

Research Instrument Scale

According to Sugiyono (2019), the Likert scale is used to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of individuals or groups regarding social phenomena. In this study, a Likert scale with a range of 1-5, which includes respondents' answers in five categories, has been applied. In this study, a Likert scale with a range of 1-5, which includes respondents' answers in five categories, namely strongly agree (5), Agree (4) Undecided (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

Operational Definition of Variables and Indicators

1. Purchase interest is the process of planning to purchase a product or service that includes planning, action, and purchase decision. Transactional interest, Referential interest, Preferential interest, Explorative interest.
2. Product completeness refers to the condition or quality of a product that is fully equipped with all components, features, information, or elements necessary to meet customer expectations and achieve intended purposes. Indicators: diversity of products sold, variety of products available, and availability of products in the market.
3. Price is determining the income of a business by determining the critical point decision in the marketing mix. Indicators: Price affordability, Price suitability with

quality, Price competitiveness, Price suitability with benefits.

4. Store location includes various marketing activities aimed at facilitating and facilitating the storage and distribution of goods and services from producers to consumers in a particular area. Indicators: access, visibility, traffic, parking, expansion, environment, competition (competitor locations), and government regulations.

5. Promotion is "a communication activity carried out by individuals or companies to the wider community, with the aim of introducing goods, services, brands, or companies, and influencing the community to buy and use these products.". Indicators: Advertising, Sales promotion, Personal selling, Public relations, Direct marketing.

Results and Discussion

Validity Test Results

The results of the instrument validity test using SPSS 27 can be seen in the table below:

Table 1. Results of Questionnaire Validity Test

Variables	Indicator	<i>r</i> Count	<i>r</i> Table	Sig	Alpha	Status
Purchase Interest (Y)	Y_1	0.763	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_2	0.769	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_3	0.756	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_4	0.753	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_5	0.740	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_6	0.754	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_7	0.678	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	Y_8	0.735	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
Product Completeness (X1)	X1_1	0.866	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_2	0.877	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_3	0.853	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X1_4	0.843	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
Price (X2)	X2_1	0.732	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_2	0.800	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_3	0.782	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X2_4	0.804	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
Store Location (X3)	X3_1	0.785	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_2	0.778	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_3	0.825	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_4	0.849	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_5	0.785	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_6	0.827	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_7	0.856	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X3_8	0.792	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
Promotion (X4)	X4_1	0.725	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_2	0.796	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_3	0.824	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_4	0.804	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_5	0.831	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_6	0.855	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid
	X4_7	0.830	0.128	0.000	0.05	Valid

Source: Data Processing (2024)

Based on these results, it can be concluded that all question items from each variable in the questionnaire are valid because the correlation value is > 0.128 in the r table and n 248 and also the significance value is < 0.05 .

Reliability Test Results

The results of reliability testing of all variable items are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Standard	Information
Purchase Interest (Y)	0.878	0.60	Reliable
Product Completeness (X1)	0.882	0.60	Reliable
Price (X2)	0.780	0.60	Reliable
Store Location (X3)	0.924	0.60	Reliable
Promotion (X4)	0.725	0.60	Reliable

Source: Data Processing (2024)

Based on the results of the reliability test listed in Table 2, each instrument item shows a Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.6, indicating that all items are reliable. Thus, all statements in the questionnaire can be considered reliable and suitable for use in collecting research data.

Normality Test Results

In this study, the results of the normality test can be seen in the presentation of data in histogram graphs, one sample Kolmogorov Smirnov and normality probability plots below:

Figure 2. Histogram of Normality Test

Source: SPSS 27 Data Processing (2024)

Based on the display of figure 2 above, it can be seen that based on the results of the normality test with the help of SPSS 27, the histogram graph is bell-shaped and symmetrical. This indicates that the data in this research variable is normally distributed.

Table 3. Results of the Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		237
Normal Parameters a,b	Mean	.0000000

	Std. Deviation	1.73059426
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.039
	Positive	.038
	Negative	-.039
Test Statistics		.039
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		

Source: SPSS 27 Data Processing (2024)

In the One Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov test, the criteria for a variable data is said to be normally distributed if the significance value (Asymp. Sig 2 Tailed) is more than 0.05 and vice versa, if the significance value (Asymp. Sig 2 Tailed) is less than 0.05 then the data is not normally distributed. In this study, it can be seen that the significance value is $0.200 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the frequency is normally distributed.

Figure 3. Normality Probability PP Plot

Source: Data Processing (2024)

The Normal PP Plot graph in Figure 3 above, the standard residual value of the regression illustrates the distribution of data following the direction of the diagonal line, so it can be concluded that the regression model used in this study is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test Results

The multicollinearity test in the explanation (Ghozali, 2021), aims to determine whether there are symptoms of correlation between independent variables in the regression model. This test can be seen from the output results of SPSS 27. The indicator of no multicollinearity is when the tolerance value is >0.1 and the VIF value <10.00 . A good regression model is one that does not show symptoms of multicollinearity.

Table 4. Results of Output Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics
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		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.233	1,047		2.134	0.034		
	Completeness Product (X1)	0.386	0.070	0.216	5,508	0.000	0.525	1,904
	Price (X2)	0.270	0.092	0.141	2,946	0.004	0.350	2,855
	Store Location (X3)	0.353	0.059	0.372	5,960	0.000	0.207	4.835
	Promotion (X4)	0.279	0.059	0.276	4.766	0.000	0.241	4.158
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Interest (Y); T Table Value (Excel): 1.97; Sig Value: 0.05								

Source: SPSS 27 Data Processing (2024)

Table 4 shows that all VIF values <10, and Tolerance values >0.1, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity phenomenon.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

To determine the presence of heteroscedasticity in a regression model, one method that can be used is the Gletsjer test. In this method, the regression model is considered free from multicollinearity if each independent variable shows a significance value above 0.05 (Sugiyono, 2021). The results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study can be seen in the table below:

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Results of the Gletsjer Test

Model		
		Sig
1	(Constant)	0.001
	Product Completeness (X1)	0.803
	Price (X2)	0.890
	Store Location (X3)	0.838
	Promotion (X4)	0.280
a. Dependent Variable: ABS_RES		

Source: SPSS 27 Data Processing (2024)

Based on table 5, the results of the Glejser test show that the model does not experience heteroscedasticity, because the significance values of all independent variables are at or above 0.05.

Multiple Linear Regression Model Analysis

Based on the results of table 9, it can be seen that the regression equation formed is:

$$Y = 2.233 + 0.386 X1 + 0.270 X2 + 0.353$$

If the independent variables, namely Product Completeness, Price, Store Location, and Promotion, are zero, then Consumer Purchase Interest at Alfamidi Manado City is 2.233; every increase in Product Completeness by 1 will increase Consumer Purchase Interest by 0.386; every increase in Price by 1 will increase Consumer Purchase Interest by 0.270; every increase in Store Location quality by 1 will increase Consumer Purchase Interest by 0.353; and every increase in Promotion by 1 will increase Consumer Purchase Interest

by 0.279, assuming other variables are constant.

F-Test Results (Simultaneous)

The results of the simultaneous F-test analysis can be seen in the table below:

Table 6. F Test Results

ANOVA						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3076.164	4	769,041	252,408	.000b
	Residual	703,815	231	3,047		
	Total	3779.979	235			
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Interest						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Product Completeness (X1), Price (X2), Store Location (X3), and Promotion (X4)						
Table F value (Excel): 2.4107; Sig Value: 0.05						

Source: Data processed by SPSS 27 (2024)

Referring to table 6, the Fcount value of 252.408 which is greater than Ftable of 2.4107 with a significance of 0.000 (less than 0.05) indicates that the variables Product Completeness (X1), Price (X2), Store Location (X3), and Promotion (X4) significantly influence Purchase Interest (Y) of Sari Roti products at Alfamidi Manado, so H1 is accepted. These results confirm that the regression model used is feasible and reliable for prediction.

t-Test Results (Partial)

The t-test (partial) is conducted to test the significance of the regression coefficient of the independent variable. From the table above, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Product Completeness (X1): The t-count value is 5.508 > t-table 1.97, with a significance of 0.000 < 0.05, so H2 is accepted. Product Completeness has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Interest.
2. Price (X2): The calculated t-value is 2.946 > t-table 1.97, with a significance of 0.004 < 0.05, so H3 is accepted. So that Price has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Interest.
3. Store Location (X3): The t-count value is 5.960 > t-table 1.97, with a significance of 0.000 < 0.05, so H4 is accepted. So that Store Location has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Interest.
4. Promotion (X4): The t-count value is 4.766 > t-table 1.97, with a significance of 0.000 < 0.05, so H5 is accepted. So that Promotion has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Interest.

Correlation Coefficient (R) and Determination Coefficient (R2)

The correlation coefficient and determination coefficient values in this research model can be seen in the model summary in the table below:

Table 7. Results of Correlation and Determination Coefficient Tests

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.902a	.814	.811	1,746
a. Predictors: (Constant), product completeness, price, store location, and promotion				
b. Dependent Variable: Purchase interest				

Source: Data processed by SPSS 27 (2024)

Based on the analysis results in Table 7 using SPSS version 27, a correlation

coefficient (R) of 0.902 was obtained, indicating that the relationship between the independent variables (product completeness, price, store location, and promotion) with purchasing interest at Alfamidi Manado City is classified as very strong (90.2%). The R Square (R^2) value of 0.814 indicates that 81.4% of the variation in consumer purchasing interest can be explained by these variables, while 18.6% is explained by other factors outside the model. Adjusted R Square is 0.811, indicating that around 81.1% of the variation in consumer purchasing interest is explained by product completeness, price, store location, and promotion, so this model is considered good enough to identify factors that influence purchasing interest.

The Influence of Product Completeness on Purchase Interest of Sari Roti Products

This study found that product completeness has a significant effect on Sari Roti's purchase interest at Alfamidi Manado City, in line with the findings of Rusdawati and Andriyani (2021), Widia, Agus and Hastuti (2021), and Utari et al. (2021). Product completeness, including variety, size, packaging, and availability, influences consumer preferences, where the more complete the product choices available, the greater the purchase interest created. Stock consistency also plays an important role in building brand loyalty, so marketing strategies need to focus on optimizing product ranges and promoting product variations that attract consumers' attention.

The Influence of Price on Purchase Interest of Sari Roti Products

This study found that price has a significant effect on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products at Alfamidi Manado City, in line with the findings of Septiyadi, Salamah, and Nujiyatillah (2022), Ruswati and Andriyani (2021), and Cahyaningtyas (2024). Price does not only reflect the numbers on the product, but also the value that consumers consider related to the quality and benefits offered. Competitive prices that are comparable to product quality will increase consumer attractiveness and purchasing interest. Conversely, prices that are considered too high without clear quality support or added value can reduce purchasing interest. Therefore, it is important for Alfamidi to conduct market research to set optimal prices that will increase purchasing interest, customer loyalty, and the long-term success of Sari Roti products..

The Influence of Store Location on Purchase Interest of Sari Roti Products

This study found that store location influences the purchase interest of Sari Roti products at Alfamidi Manado City, in line with the findings of Alnahhal et al. (2024), Pitanatri and Pitana (2024), and Wulandari and Nastian (2021). A strategic and easily accessible location makes it easier for consumers to reach the product, increasing their chances of buying. Locations close to residential areas, shopping centers, or high-traffic areas can attract more visitors. Factors such as visibility, accessibility, ease of parking, and public transportation are also important. A strategic location, coupled with the advantages of Sari Roti products in quality and price, can create additional appeal, even in a competitive environment. Social and cultural aspects around the location also influence purchasing decisions. Therefore, Alfamidi managers need to choose the right location to increase purchase interest and the long-term success of the Sari Roti brand.

The Influence of Promotion on Purchase Interest of Sari Roti Products

This study found that promotion has an effect on purchasing interest in Sari Roti products at Alfamidi Manado City, in line with the findings of Diansyah and Utami (2022), Usman (2021), and Mansur and Dewi (2023). Promotion functions as a tool to convey information about products, their benefits, and advantages. Good promotional efforts, such as discounts, bundling, and campaigns on social media, can attract

consumers' attention and encourage them to try the product, which in turn increases purchasing interest. In addition, promotions that highlight the quality, variety of variants, and uniqueness of the product can influence consumer perceptions. Promotional activities that involve direct interaction with consumers, such as product sampling, are also effective in building emotional connections and increasing the likelihood of repeat purchases. By utilizing social media and other channels, well-planned promotions can increase purchasing interest and strengthen loyalty to the Sari Roti brand

Conclusions

1. Product Completeness, Price, Store Location, and Promotion simultaneously influence the interest in purchasing Sari Roti products at Alfamidi Manado City.
2. Product completeness has a significant influence on purchasing interest, with consistent product variety and availability being the main factors.
3. Competitive pricing influences purchasing interest, with consumers preferring products that offer the best value in terms of quality and price.
4. The strategic and easily accessible store location increases the chances of purchasing and contributes to the success of the Sari Roti brand.
5. Effective promotions, including advertising, discounts, sampling, and social media, influence purchase intention by increasing awareness and reinforcing positive perceptions.

Suggestion

1. Educational institutions should integrate marketing and product management materials into the curriculum so that students understand effective marketing strategies.
2. It is expected that educational institutions will collaborate with the Sari Roti company to conduct research related to market trends and consumer behavior.
3. Educational institutions can develop product marketing training programs that involve industry to provide deeper insights to students and the community.
4. Sari Roti management needs to develop an integrated marketing strategy with various promotional channels to increase brand awareness and attract consumers.
5. Companies must provide training to employees so that they can convey interesting information and provide positive experiences to consumers.
6. Management is advised to collect and analyze consumer feedback to understand their preferences and improve products and marketing strategies

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